

Localizing Community Resilience within the Digital Humanities: Examples from the Penghu Archipelago

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The ongoing climate change and its consequences, such as the increase of atmospheric energy, the rise of the sea level, as well as the change of wind patterns and sea currents have triggered multiple responses in politics, societies and research. In academia, research started to shift from the technical conception of *vulnerability* to a culturally rooted notion of *resilience* (Agdar 2000, Berkes and Ross 2013). Part of this research tries to understand how local communities have in the past, through evolution and adaptation, developed, maintained and transmitted their *resilience* (Bixia 2013, Streiter et al. 2021), and which role culture plays in this process. The aim of researching resilience-in-cultures is thus to understand the empowering role of culture in our transforming world and to potentially assist communities in a phase of accelerated transformation, for which the normal life-cycles of cultural adaptation are potentially too slow.

Community resilience, for which most resilient or endangered communities might themselves have no specific word, (Wairama et al. 2021), nor a designed committee or infrastructure, is hard to describe or quantify. For the operationalization of resilience, researchers in the past had to rely on their intuition and frequently fell back to ad-hoc observations of cultural traits which could be theoretically linked to resilience. The resilience of a community, however, can be apprehended neither from its material, social or cultural components, especially if these are depicted as isolated or static (Uddin et al. 2020). These components instead are wheels in a system that needs to be characterized first, in order to create appropriate etic data categories that allow for a comparison and analysis of culture-specific, emic phenomena in relation to resilience (Gómez-Baggethun 2012), doing so in a systematic and replicable way. We thus propose a model of resilience which leads to a methodology and a data collection method as well as formalization, archiving, modeling and computing.

Resilience, as the source for beneficial transformation of communities, lives through the dynamics and self-changing mechanisms provided from within a culture, cf. Folke (2006). While previous approaches have seen culture as supportive of resilience, or partially overlapping with resilience, we understand culture as a specific, “culture-specific” framework of resilience. Resilience thus projects through its culture-specific framework, a cul-

ture-specific implementation of resilience, into and can be understood through observable cultural practices, such as classifying, naming, monitoring, communication, recording history, predicting, preparing, adapting to and learning from external pressures.

The proposal we develop here is based on our decade-long digital fieldwork on the Penghu archipelago and the attempts to make sense of this data (Streiter and Goudin 2013). Recently, we could show that data on the settlements of Penghu can be modeled in terms of socio-cognitive grammars (Streiter et al. 2021). The rules, which collectively define the grammar, are individually defined by a condition expressed as environmental feature, a theme, that is a structure to be placed into space, and the instruction, the prescribed placement. Through the materialization of the rules, i.e. the placement of houses, gardens that follow these rules on Penghu, the range of grammar rules can be localized in time and space.

Figure 1: A rule specifying that *U-shaped walled gardens*, locally called “caizhai”, face the wind

Figure 2: Localizing the materialization of rules, i.e. the placement of houses or gardens, through annotated and geo-referenced media files.

Figure 3: Mapping the spatial range of Rule 4, gardens that face the wind.

Stratificational variations of grammar rules exist at different levels, e.g. community, island, and region, i.e. Rule 4 is a regional rule with a few exceptions in a few communities. In addition to

this vertical connection of grammars, we can observe a horizontal isomorphism, e.g. through similarities found in neighboring villages, plus a parallel isomorphism, e.g. for houses and temples within one community. In our fieldwork we thus document a network of grammars for a great variety of themes, e.g. houses, gardens, which is the foundation for experimenting, evaluation, learning, exchange, adaptation and thus, as a network of potential changes, for the resilience of a community.

Magong, Shanshui

Magong, Suogang

Xiyu, Zhuwan

Xiyu, Hejie

Figure 4: Vertical isomorphism of grammars. The central generals of a) Shanshui and b) Suogang, two neighboring villages on the Pengnan peninsula, and of c) Zhuwan and d) Hejie, two neighboring villages on Xiyu Island.

To trace the similarity of vertical, horizontal or parallel grammars through empiric data, one has to establish and compare the rules of these grammars. If uniformly formalized in if-then statements, the similarities among rules of different grammars can be described in terms of analogy, e.g. small wind -> small wall vs. big wind -> big wall. Analogies thus describe the transformation of socio-cognitive grammars in a formal, cognitive and computational way. In addition, we use the term *cultural operator* to describe how rule transformations materialize with respect to their focus, scale and agency, and thus how they affect a society.

We currently distinguish cultural operators along three dimensions: The *focus*, the *scale* and the *agency*. The *focus* describes a cultural operator as either transfer, i.e. change of object or site, or adaptation, i.e. the change of method or tool. The *scale* refers to downsizing versus upscaling, i.e. the reduction or multiplication of the scale. The *agency* distinguishes *recuperation*, also known as coopting, i.e. governmental appropriation of a local practice, usually associated with upscaling, and *assimilation*, i.e. the replacement of a local practice under social pressure. These three dimensions represent theoretically eight possible classes for cultural operators, with a very uneven statistical distribution.

Figure 5: Possible analogy relations between practices of wind protection.

<p>Cultural Operator: Transfer Analogy: House - Garden Site: House - Garden Method: Wall with doors and windows - Wall Theme: Wind and rain - Wind</p>	See Figure 6	<p>Cultural Operator: Upscaling & Recuperation, Transfer, Adaptation Analogy: Garden - Field Site: Garden - Field Method: Wall - Rampart Theme: Wind NE - Wind NE</p>
See Figure 7	See Figure 8	See Figure 9
<p>Cultural Operator: Example Downsizing, Transfer, Adaptation Analogy: Garden - Plant Site: Garden - Plant Method: Wall - Stones Theme: Wind NE - Wind NE</p>	See Figure 10	<p>Cultural Operator: Transfer, Adaptation Analogy: Garden - Village Site: Garden - Village Method: Wall - Wall with gates Theme: Wind NE - Wind NE</p>

Figure 6: The Japanese colonial government tried to upscale gardens to regularly shaped fields.

Figure 7: Broken houses are turned into gardens. Example from Xiaochi, Baisha.

Figure 8: Walled gardens facing the wind. Example from Jibei Island.

Figure 9: Wind wall of Huxi village with gates for humans to pass.

Figure 10: A cabbage plant protected by two stones, Jibei Island.

The resilience of a community, we thus propose, can be approached through the wealth of analogy relations that exist between the rules of socio-cognitive grammars of a local culture, cf. Elmqvist et. al (2003) and Leslie and McCabe (2013). However, not all cultural operators are equally valuable for a community. Especially a recuperation with upscaling might be received with criticism, by community members as by academic evaluations. A further evaluation of the contribution of cultural operators to community resilience will thus be required. Overall, our innovative approach provides resilience research with a cultural perspective that can benefit from the wealth of tools and techniques developed in the Digital Humanities. Discovering and analyzing cultural operations, e.g. in terms of analogies, helps to describe community resilience in a systematic way and thus to lay a solid foundation for data collection and analysis.

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